

**Deliverable D1.10:
Policy Brief**

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POLICY BRIEF
RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

INTRODUCTION: PROJECT TITLE AND PROJECT OBJECTIVES

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01

TOPIC: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01-01: Research infrastructure services to enable R&I addressing main challenges and EU priorities

Area: RI services for innovative applications of nanoscience and nanotechnology

PROJECT: Research Infrastructure Access in NANoscience & nanotechnology (RIANA)
<https://riana-project.eu/>

PROJECT objectives:

RIANA provides single-entry-point access to a coordinated portfolio of nanoscience and nanotechnology research infrastructures across Europe, with the following specific objectives:

- 👍 Provide highly customized trans-national access (TA) to 69 research infrastructures distributed across 22 European countries, totaling > 35 000 hours of instrument access and > 5 000 000 CPU hours of virtual access (VA) to high-power computing.
- 👍 Close knowledge, innovation, network, and methodology gaps for users from academia and industry through a network of 22 Junior Scientists providing one-to-one Science Service from proposal preparation to data analysis and dissemination, enabling effective use of Research Infrastructures.
- 👍 Support industrial users via a Platform of Industrial Contact Officers (PICO) and dedicated pilot studies on TRL upscaling and interoperability of nanotechnology techniques.
- 👍 Maintain a 1 M€ reserve to extend access flexibly, in response to user requests, to additional facilities not foreseen at proposal time.
- 👍 Translate European values from FAIR data (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) to DEI (Diversity, Equity, Inclusion) into practice at Research Infrastructures upholding highest ethical standards in challenge-driven research.
- 👍 Develop a roadmap (D1.4) for the future of nanoscience and nanotechnology access at European research infrastructures beyond the project end.

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POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Implementation of research infrastructures**

Not applicable as RIANA does not implement new research infrastructures (RIs).

- **Access to research infrastructures**

RIANA provides single-entry-point access to 69 RI in the fields of nanoscience and nanotechnology in 22 European countries, with > 35 000 hours of trans-national access (TA) and > 5 000 000 CPU hours of virtual access (VA) committed over the project. Additionally, a 1 M€ reserve is held back for flexible TA/VA allocation to adapt to proven user requests through the project. Access is organized in a permanently open rolling call, and pre-proposals / proposals / reviews are continuously submitted and dealt with for timely access provision.

Remarkably, the sheer size of the consortium has not turned out to be a major issue but is manageable.

Access is supported by a network of 22 Junior Scientists in the Smart Science Cluster, providing one-to-one Science Service from proposal preparation through experiment, data analysis and dissemination – lowering the practical barrier to inexperienced users and enabling them to perform sophisticated experiments only advanced users could do otherwise.

Recommendation: Continue and strengthen EU support for the people and services that make access to research infrastructures effective — notably networks of dedicated user-facing scientists such as the RIANA Smart Science Cluster — alongside investment in the underlying RIs, so that the considerable resources committed to RI access translate into the largest possible scientific and societal impact.

- **Funding of research infrastructures**

Two RIANA features inform RI funding models. (1) RI hosts contribute on average 2/3 of the actual access costs as in-kind contribution against the negotiated discounted RIANA access rate, and the EC contributes 1/3. The EC contribution is considered borderline low – excellent and expensive RI may not be available for future projects anymore at these reimbursement rates. (2) A 1 M€ reserve is held at consortium level for flexible allocation to access not foreseen at proposal time, including at non-European facilities. This reserve proves to be an excellent approach dealing with dynamic developments.

Recommendation: In future calls, retain both (1) the in-kind cost-share model but with a higher fraction of EC-reimbursed costs and (2) an explicit reserve mechanism. They have proven effective in keeping per-hour costs predictable and in preserving flexibility to meet dynamically changing user demand.

- **International co-operation of research infrastructures**

RIANA lives international co-operation of RIs daily beyond the political borders of the European Union: partners of the UK and Switzerland are already full beneficiaries of RIANA, and a US partner (Brookhaven National Laboratory) may offer access to a worldwide unique instrument in RIANA from

the next amendment on. Many inter-RI co-operation activities have been prompted by RIANA already, and international co-operation is formalized at the level of the Industry Contact Officer (PICO) and Junior Scientist network that operates as the Smart Science Cluster distributed across Europe. Finally, the strong pull of researchers from widening countries for access to RIANA RIs demonstrates the excellence of Europe's RIs and provides a strong leverage for actual impact at the international level.

Recommendation: Clarify the funding rules for non-European partners early in the call cycle – current arrangements require workarounds – and expand the model where funding can be allocated flexibly to non-EU facilities to meet user demand.

- **Employment and skills in research infrastructures**

RIANA supports around 22 Junior Scientist positions (most at the postdoc level) distributed across the consortium (16 defined at kick-off and 6 allocated in response to user demand), providing cross-disciplinary training and user support beyond RI offers. This concept has proven effective both for excellence in user support and for the further career of the Junior Scientists, who gain valuable experience in world-class laboratories and considerably strengthen their professional networks.

Recommendation: Continue funding cross-RI early-career positions integrated in TA/VA projects as the Smart Science Cluster in RIANA. Consider connecting such RI-based Smart Science Clusters from INFRA-SERV calls with other programs, e.g., Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Postdoctoral Fellowships.

- **Greening of research infrastructures**

While greening is not at the core of RIANA, minor contributions include 5 000 000 CPU hours of virtual access to high-power computing infrastructures, allowing computational nanoscience to be pursued without travel, and the RIANA Smart Science Cluster supports remote experiments and data analysis to minimize traveling, though in-person training and experiments proves to be more sustainable in view of training on the long run.

Recommendation: Continue EU support for hybrid and remote access in INFRA-SERV calls and recognize the associated personnel costs explicitly in future budgets.

- **Interaction of research infrastructures with industry**

- (1) RIANA runs a dedicated TA/VA scheme targeting Small and Medium-sized Companies (SMEs).
- (2) RIANA runs a Platform of Industrial Contact Officers (PICO) modelled on practice at large-scale RIs, with dedicated Industry Contact Officers (ICOs) supporting industrial users on contractual, technical and IP matters.
- (3) Pilot studies on TRL upscaling and interoperability are run under WP 4 to evaluate and foster access modes for industrial use.

For details about the interaction of RI with industry, we refer to deliverables D4.1, D4.2, and D4.3 that will be published soon on zenodo¹ and the RIANA webpage.²

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/riana/>

² <https://riana-project.eu/project-deliverables/>

The current INFRA-SERV call only allows SMEs as industrial users. This is unfortunate, as Europe struggles attracting and keeping larger companies: particularly in fields such as photovoltaics and semiconductor devices that would could perfectly profit from RI access offered in RIANA and are of strategic relevance for Europe, relevant industries are excluded from RI access, which sets Europe back in the international competition both in R&D and industrial exploitation of research.

Recommendation: Review the SME-only subsidy boundary for INFRA-SERV calls and allow TA/VA access for industry in general, either as part of Horizon Europe or as part of a dedicated scheme e.g. in the future European Competitiveness Fund.

- **ERIC legal framework**

Not applicable as RIANA does not operate as an ERIC.

- **Technology development, data and digital services, digitalisation**

Not applicable as RIANA focuses on effective RI access provision, not on technology development.

- **Level of connection of your RI to EOSC**

RIANA beneficiaries have taken a leading role in open science from early on, and best-practice EOSC and FAIR principles are followed and promoted by RIANA – although EOSC is not a primary objective of RIANA per se. Task 6.3 targets EOSC connection explicitly: it extends FAIR data adoption among the nanoscience community by providing recommendations for aligning facility policies with EOSC as detailed in deliverable D6.2.³ Whenever possible, data generated within RIANA are FAIR and publications including all public deliverables are published via the RIANA channel on zenodo.⁴

- **Contribution to other research areas and to broader EU priorities**

At the project level, RIANA is well aligned with the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and the Advanced Materials 2030 Initiative, and close ties exist to partner projects including ReMade@ARI and NEPHEWS.

At the user level, RIANA users tackle a breadth of scientific questions matching EU priorities from power electronics design to batteries, from nano-toxicity to drug development.

Recommendation: Continue to support broad priority- and challenge-driven RI access. While narrow definitions of research areas hinder scientific curiosity and success, broad definitions such as in RIANA are ideal to attract excellent RI users who effectively contribute to EU priorities with an open mind.

³ M. Ounsy, G. Garcia Lopez, T. Minniberger, & M. Stuckelberger (2026). RIANA Deliverable D6.2: FAIR Data Guidelines. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19645041>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/riana/>

- **Sustainability of research infrastructures**

The sustainability of the RIs in RIANA per se is mostly granted as infrastructures of national relevance, and deliverable D1.4 (NANO Roadmap, due Dec. 2027) will set out a strategy for the future of nanoscience and nanotechnology access. Yet, the sustainability of the RI access through EU projects such as RIANA is a major challenge: many structures have been set up efficiently for the RIANA project, including the RIANA single-entry-point with its entire proposal review workflow, the Smart Science Cluster, and the Platform of Industrial Contact Officers, all of which are intended to outlast the project. Unfortunately, they risk ceasing operation at the end of the project due to a lack of sustainable funding. Future projects may re-build similar structures, which is not a sustainable concept.

Recommendation: Provide continuity funding instruments specifically for cross-RI access and services. The call HORIZON-INFRA-2027-SERV-01-01 goes into a good direction, but longer project duration and adequate funding for such broad areas are required for truly sustainable RI access.